

Research of the Characteristics of the Intake of Air-Jet Engine and its Influences on the Engine Performances

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Over the last decade, aircraft gas turbine engines have achieved a high degree of excellence and reliability and have become the main type of aircraft propulsion. Numerous experimental studies, which are carried out on a special test stand or in factory testing of experimental and serial engines or in flight tests, can enrich the theory of gas turbine engines and can refine the original idea of the workflow of engine as a whole and individual components. A large amount of experimental data is required to improve the thermo and gas-dynamic calculation methods of engines. Currently, an engineer, working in the field of research, design and development of aircraft gas turbine engine, needs much effort to develop the methods for calculating the working process and the characteristics of the engines and their components. The manner in which the inlet and engine designs are integrated plays a key role in determining the degree to which propulsion system and aircraft operational goals are ultimately realized in the production model.

1. Introduction

The air intake is essentially a fluid flow duct whose task is to process the airflow in a way that ensures the engine functions properly to generate thrust. Depending on the engine arrangement and aircraft design speed, great varieties of intake shapes exist. Due to the influence of intake flow on overall aircraft performance, responsibility for intake design rests with the aircraft manufacturer, not the engine maker. However, both partners work closely together to achieve an optimum solution. The intake must be designed to provide the appropriate amount of airflow required by the engine, to convert efficiently kinetic energy of incoming stream into pressure energy and, furthermore, that this flow when leaving the intake section to enter the compressor will be uniform, stable, and of high quality. These conditions must be met not only during all phase of flight, but also on the ground, with the aircraft at rest and the engine demanding maximum thrust prior to take-off. Gas-dynamics losses in the process of inhibition of air stream (Intake efficiency) can be evaluated as the coefficient of total pressure recovery: $\sigma_{in} = P_1^*/P_0^*$, where P_1^* – total pressure at the compressor face; P_0^* – total pressure of undisturbed flow ahead of the intake. The total pressure loss depends on the flight speed and design of intake and the rise of the losses in the intake make worse the engine performance.

2. Experiment

The study of effect of characteristics of intake was accomplished on the base of design parameters of 5kN turbojet engine. Intake design was accomplished by applying the laws of fluid dynamics with optimum conditions for subsonic flight speed. The following two formulae were used to design the profile of intake as shown in Fig. 1:

$$\frac{r}{R_{out}} = \frac{R_0}{R_{out}} + \left(1 - \frac{R_0}{R_{out}}\right) \sqrt{1 - \left(1 - \frac{R_{out}}{l} \frac{x}{R_{out}}\right)^2} \quad (\text{Outer contour})$$

$$\frac{r}{R_{out}} = \frac{R_0}{R_{out}} - \left(\frac{R_0}{R_{in}} - 1 \right) \frac{R_{in}}{R_{out}} \sqrt{1 - \left(1 - \frac{R_{in}}{l_{in}} \frac{x}{R_{in}} \right)^2} \quad (\text{Inner contour})$$

Fig. 1 Geometrical parameters of axisymmetric air intake

Fig. 2 Configuration of unstructured grids of the intake, generated for the CFD Analysis

Defining the losses at the intake was carried out by the numerical experiments using OpenFOAM: an Open Source CFD tool. OpenFOAM stands for "Open Source Field Operation and Manipulation".

The configuration of unstructured grids generated for CFD analysis near the intake is shown in Fig. 2. The numerical studies were carried out under various incoming airflow speed within the range of Mach number 0~0.7.

The effects of total pressure loss on the characteristics of engine components and the engine performance were carried out by the method of small variation. In this case, the effects of total pressure loss on the thrust R and specific fuel consumption rate C_e were studied. If the coefficient of total pressure recovery is increased by $\delta\sigma$ %, thus this will make relatively changes in thrust by $(\delta R/\delta\sigma) \times \delta\sigma$ % and in specific fuel consumption rate by $(\delta C_e/\delta\sigma) \times \delta\sigma$ %, where $(\delta R/\delta\sigma)$ and $(\delta C_e/\delta\sigma)$ – coefficients of influence.

3. Results and Discussion

Some results of the numerical experiments of the intake at various flight velocities are shown below. At first, the simulation of airflow at the pre-take-off static condition with the engine delivering maximum thrust was studied.

Fig. 3 Velocity distribution diagram (M=0)

Fig. 4 Static pressure distribution diagram (M=0)

Fig. 5 Total pressure distribution diagram (M=0)

Fig. 6 Streamlines of velocity (M=0)

As the ambient air in this particular case is normally at rest, the air within the intake must be accelerated to the velocity required by the compressor. The air is drawn from around the nacelle, even from behind the intake lip.

The following results shows the simulation of airflow when the flight Mach number equals to 0.3, which is slower than the velocity required by the compressor.

Fig. 7 Velocity distribution diagram (M = 0.3)

Fig. 8 Static pressure distribution diagram (M=0.3)

Fig. 9 Total pressure distribution diagram (M=0.3)

Fig. 10 Streamlines of velocity (M=0.3)

As long as the aircraft has not achieved a velocity suitable for the compressor, airflow will continue to be accelerated within the intake, though to a lesser degree. Because the airflow within the streamtube corresponds to mass flow rate of engine, a contraction of the streamtube will be observed, the bounding streamlines of which will terminate in stagnation points on the cowl.

The following results shows the simulation of airflow when the flight Mach number equals to 0.6, which is faster than the velocity required by the compressor.

Fig. 11 Velocity distribution diagram (M = 0.6)

Fig. 12 Static pressure distribution diagram (M=0.6)

Fig. 13 Total pressure distribution diagram (M=0.6)

Fig. 14 Streamlines of velocity (M=0.6)

At this flight Mach numbers, airflow approaching the engine will exceed the velocity required by the compressor. The cross-section area of streamtube at upstream infinity is markedly smaller than the cross-section at the entrance of the intake. This will result in a deceleration of the flow immediately upstream of the intake, with pressure increasing before the airflow enters the intake.

The calculated results of characteristics of the intake are expressed in Table 1 and dependence of total pressure loss on Mach number M is shown in Fig 15.

Fig. 15 Coefficient of total pressure recovery depending on the flight Mach number

Table 1 Results of numerical experiments under various flight velocity

M	-	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
V	m/sec	0	34	68	102	136	170	204	238
σ_{in}	-	0.977	0.983	0.987	0.989	0.990	0.991	0,991	0,984

The calculated results of characteristics of the coefficients of influence of single spool turbojet engine with critical pressure drop in reaction nozzle depending on the flight Mach number are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Coefficients of influence of losses in the intake on the parameters of turbojet engine

	$\delta\sigma_{inlet}$						
M	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6
$\Delta\pi_{turbine}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$\Delta\pi_{compressor}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
$\Delta\pi_{nozzle}$	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
δm_{air}	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
$\delta T_{compressor}$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
δT_3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
δR	1.36	1.377	1.394	1.411	1.428	1.445	1.462
$\delta m_{turbine}$	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
δC_e	-0.36	-0.377	-0.394	-0.411	-0.428	-0.445	-0.462

Variations of coefficient of influences of thrust and specific fuel consumption rate are shown in Fig 16.

Fig. 16 Influence of coefficient of total pressure recovery on thrust and specific fuel consumption rate under various the flight Mach number

By using the calculated coefficients of influence and the characteristics of the intake from numerical experiments, thrust (Fig. 17) and specific fuel consumption rate (Fig. 18) of turbojet engine are plotted against the flight Mach number.

The coefficients of total pressure recover in the intake of modern aircrafts are found to be higher value of $\sigma_{in} = 0.98-0.995$. With the rise of coefficients of total pressure recovery, thrust of engine increases, mean while the specific fuel consumption rate decreases. Minimum loss is found when the flight velocity equals the velocity of air at entry to compressor.

Fig. 17 Dependence of thrust on the total pressure loss in the intake σ_{in}

Fig. 18 Dependence of specific fuel consumption rate on the total pressure loss in the intake σ_{in}

4. Conclusion

The profiling of the intake system of 5kN turbojet was carried out. The total pressure losses in the intake between the range of velocities of incoming stream ($M = 0\sim 0.7$) was studied by using OpenFOAM: an open source CFD tool. The effects of total pressure loss on the thrust R and specific fuel consumption rate C_e of engine and were calculated by the method of small variation. It was found that the rise of coefficients of total pressure recovery lead to the increase in thrust of engine and decrease in the specific fuel consumption rate.

In conclusion, at the stage of thermodynamics calculation, assumed coefficients, which represent the losses of components of gas turbine engine, do not always agree with the values obtained at the stage of bench refining process. Thus, it is required much time for development process. Evaluation of the losses at those components such as intake can be made by means of the computational experiments using CFD tools. It reduces time required for development process. The use of small variations method allows us to obtain the effect of losses on the characteristics of engine with sufficient accuracy without carrying out the complex gas-dynamics calculations. It reduces time required for gas-dynamics calculations. Also using open source CFD tool like OpenFOAM make possible to do numerical studies without the need of license, thus avoid the cost for commercial one.

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References

- [1] Borisenka A. I., Gas Dynamics of Engines, (In Russian) Moscow, **454** (1962) 793.
- [2] A. Y. Cherkez , Engineering Calculations of Gas Turbine Engines using Method of Small Variation, (In Russian) Moscow, **1** (1965) 354.
- [3] Min Thaw Tun, Research of the Characteristics of the Inlet and Exhaust Systems of Air-Jet Engine and their Influences on the Engine Performances, BMSTU (Kaluga), (2012)